

NASCENT HYDROGEN. PART I. REDUCTION OF POTASSIUM PERMANGANATE
BY NASCENT HYDROGEN FROM SULPHURIC ACID AND METALS :
ZINC AND CADMIUM

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The greater activity of nascent hydrogen from Zn and H_2SO_4 than Cd and H_2SO_4 in the reduction of $KMnO_4$ is due to the effective concentration of hydrogen atoms being greater.

The study of the nascent state of hydrogen is an old one and a number of interesting experiments have been devised to demonstrate the reducing powers of nascent hydrogen over molecular hydrogen. No less than six theories have been put forward from time to time. A few of them merit consideration.

A. Laurent, and P. A. Favre and J. T. Silberman in 1846 suggested that hydrogen absorbed on palladium was more active since it was in the atomic condition. Tommasi, (*Ber.* 1898, 31, 345, 1878; *Chem. News*, 1879, 40, 245; *J. phys. chem.*, 1897, 1, 555) has emphasised the fact that this explanation does not make it clear why nascent hydrogen from zinc and hydrochloric acid is able to reduce chlorates and bromates to their respective chlorides and bromides—while hydrogen from sodium amalgam will not do so. M. Berthelot considers that the liberation of hydrogen is a secondary reaction while the main reaction is the formation of a complex with the substance to be reduced. He calls these complexes by *les systems reducteurs*. In case of reduction of potassium chlorates zinc and sulphuric acid the system— $Zn-H_2SO_4-KClO_3$ changes into the system $ZnSO_4-H_2-KCl-H_2O$. However in cases like

no hydrogen is evolved. Tommasi (*loc. cit.*) argues that the reducing properties of nascent hydrogen depend on the nature of the reaction from which it is derived and that the greater activity of hydrogen in *Statu nascendi* arises from the momentary association of hydrogen with n calories of energy liberated by the reaction. According to him the term nascent hydrogen therefore is synonymous with $\frac{H^{+n}}$ calories. The difference in reducing properties of hydrogen produced by different reactions is determined by the amount of heat liberated in the reaction.

From this it appears that the activity of nascent hydrogen with Cd, Zn and Mg and sulphuric acid should stand in the ratio of 1 : 1.7 : 5.0.

However Tommasi (*loc. cit.*) has not been able to hold this view in all cases and assumes in some cases $M + n$ calories where M is the metal. Studies on overvoltage phenomena by a number of workers (Tafel and Newmann, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1905, 50, 713; Bohninger, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1906, 12, 745; Haber, *ibid.*, 1902, 8, 539; Lewis and Jackson, *Proc. Amer. Acad.*,

1906, 4, 398; Reichstein, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1910, 16, 927) have revealed that at the cathode the following reactions occur :

The lowering of overvoltage by impurities is to increase the rate of the second reaction and thus decreasing the concentration of hydrogen atoms at any time. Hence J. W. Mellor ("Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. I, p. 334, Longmans, 1920) concludes that "the so-called nascent hydrogen is assumed to consist of electrically neutral atoms (mono) of hydrogen and the difference in the nascent hydrogen derived from different sources is due to the effective concentration of mono-atomic hydrogen which in turn is determined by the rate of conversion of the mono-atomic into ordinary hydrogen".

There has been no quantitative studies on the kinetics of the reduction by nascent hydrogen to prove if the difference in activity of nascent hydrogen from different sources is due to the difference in heat of reaction or difference in concentration of mono-atomic hydrogen. It is proposed in this investigation to study the kinetics of the reduction of potassium permanganate by nascent hydrogen liberated by the action of zinc and cadmium on sulphuric acid, to throw some light on the problem.

EXPERIMENTAL

The reaction vessel consists of 250 c.c. gas cylinder held in an electrically heated thermostat maintained at 30° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). The metals were obtained in the form of rods of 1/8" thick. Zinc rod was pure quality E. Merck. It was difficult to obtain pure cadmium. Various samples were tried and finally a pure sample (Merck) having sp. gr. 8.65 was taken. Pure material has a sp. gr. of 8.64. The metal rod was fixed to the axis of the stirring motor so that it was both reacting and at the same time stirring the permanganate solution. By a series of trials, it was found workable to use 50 ml. of 0.8859*N*/4 permanganate solution made up to 250 ml. with 4*N*-H₂SO₄. The stirrer was held in the reaction vessel and the motor switched on. The solution was poured quickly into the vessel so that always the same length of rod 4 1/2" was immersed in the solution. The time was noted and at intervals of each 60 seconds 2 ml. of the solution were pipetted out quickly and kept in a test-tube, thus insulating the solution after reaction. It was noticed in all cases that brisk evolution of hydrogen gas took place only after the completion of the reduction of permanganate. The solutions insolated at the end of each 60 sec. were found to slowly precipitate a brown hydrated manganese dioxide. The solutions were centrifuged and the clear solution above the precipitate was decanted into the fixed cell of a Heillege colour comparator and the original unreacted solution taken in the Wedge cell of the apparatus. At various intervals of the reaction, the concentration of the unreacted permanganate solution was read off as scale reading in the comparator after matching the intensity. The velocity coefficients were calculated between each interval. The results are reproducible and the table contains representative data.

TABLE I

Time, \	Zinc		Cadmium	
	Scale readings.	Velocity coefficient (<i>k</i>).	Scale readings.	Velocity coefficient (<i>k</i>).
0 secs.	13.50	—	13.5	—
90	8.10	0.00833	—	—
120	4.45	0.00840	8.3	0.00398
180	2.45	0.00835	6.0	0.00428
240	0.40	0.00800	5.0	0.00383
300	—	—	3.4	0.00394
360	—	—	2.1	0.00406
420	—	—	0.8	0.00404
Average		0.00827		0.00402

From the results described in the above table the nascent hydrogen from zinc is twice as active as that from cadmium. On plotting the scale readings against time, it could be read off from the graph (not shown here) that time for half reaction with cadmium is 81 sec. and with zinc is 162 sec. This shows that the effective concentration of nascent hydrogen (if it be mono-atomic) is twice in the $Zn + H_2SO_4$ than in that of $Cd + H_2SO_4$. In the same time under identical conditions zinc displaces twice the number of atoms of hydrogen as cadmium from H_2SO_4 . The reaction then has to be represented :

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